

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds.

Part I.

BY

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The number of known compounds containing two dissimilar heterocyclic rings in their molecules is not great and it was thought interesting to study how in such compounds the properties of the different heterocyclic nuclei were affected by one another.

Aromatic *ortho*-diamines like *o*-phenylenediamine being well adapted for the formation of heterocyclic compounds, 2:3-diamino-phenazine (Ullmann and Mauthner, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4302), which already contains one heterocyclic ring, was chosen as the starting material. The idea was to introduce various types of new heterocyclic rings through the two *ortho*-amino groups and find out how the properties of the already existing azine ring were influenced by the newly entering hetero-ring and *vice versa*.

It has now been found that 2:3-diamino-phenazine is not so well adapted as *ortho*-phenylenediamine for the formation of heterocyclic compounds. Evidently the existing azine ring in the molecule influences the otherwise easily reactive *ortho*-amino groups.

2:3-Diamino-phenazine has now been condensed with phthalic, camphoric, 1:8-naphthalic and diphenic anhydrides (*cf.* Rupe and Thiess, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4287; Sachs, *Annalen*, 1909, 365, 117). On an examination of the properties of the acidoylene-phenazino-iminazoles so obtained it is found that in their molecules the properties of the heterocyclic azine ring are to some extent modified by the introduction of the acidoylene-iminazole ring and

vice versa. They are all yellow, *i.e.*, possess almost the same colour as diamino-phenazine.

2:3-Diamino-phenazine has also been condensed with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-dimethyl aminobenzaldehyde and the properties of the resulting iminazoles studied.

An attempt was next made to prepare $\alpha\beta$ -diketo-2:3-phenazino-dihydroquinoxaline by the condensation of 2:3-diamino-phenazine with oxalyl chloride and introduce further heterocyclic rings through the *o*-diketonic group of that body; but the condensation product probably tautomerises readily to the dihydroxy-quinoxoline form and therefore does not show any of the reactions characteristic of the *ortho*-diketones. Attempts to condense *o*-phenylenediamine with the dihydroxy-azino-azine were also unsuccessful.

2:3-Diaminophenazine and nitrous acid form an azoimide derivative fairly easily. But it does not form cyclic guanidine derivative with mustard oils. With *o*-tolyl mustard oil it yields a thiourea derivative. Iminazole derivatives were not obtained by the action of either acetic anhydride (*cf.* Fischer and Hepp, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 357) or benzoylchloride on 2:3-diaminophenazine. Chlorocarbonic ester or sulphur dioxide has no action on the diaminophenazine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Camphoroylene-2:3-phenazino-iminazole.

An intimate mixture of 2:3-diaminophenazine (1 gm.) and camphoric anhydride (1.5 gms.) was heated

under reflux in an oil-bath to 240° , when it melted. The temperature was then quickly lowered and kept at 210° for half an hour. After cooling, the melt was repeatedly extracted with ether. The solid obtained on evaporating the ethereal solution was boiled several times with water and filtered hot. The residue separated from dilute alcohol in beautiful yellow needles, melting at $215-219^{\circ}$ with previous shrinking at 202° .

It is insoluble in water, but soluble in ether or alcohol. It gives a greenish-black colouration with strong sulphuric acid (Found : $N=15.75$. $C_{22}H_{20}ON_4$ requires $N=15.73$ per cent.).

o-Benzoylene-2 : 3-phenazino-iminazole.

The light-green mass, produced by heating 1 gm. of 2:3-diaminophenazine and 1 gm. of phthalic anhydride for two hours at $210-230^{\circ}$ after having been repeatedly boiled with water and then thoroughly washed with warm glacial acetic acid, crystallised from nitrobenzene in bright-yellow needles, not melting below 300° .

It is insoluble in water or ether, very slightly soluble in alcohol, benzene or acetic acid, and readily soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives an intense red colouration (Found : $N=17.92$. $C_{20}H_{16}ON_4$ requires $N=17.89$ per cent.).

o-Naphthoylene-2 : 3-phenazino-iminazole.

The mass produced by heating 2 : 3-diaminophenazine (1 gm.) and naphthalic anhydride (1.5 gms.) under reflux at $270^{\circ}-280^{\circ}$ for one hour and a half was successively boiled with alcohol and glacial acetic acid and filtered hot. The residue crystallised from nitrobenzene as bright-yellow needles, not melting below 300° .

It is insoluble in water, ether, alcohol or acetic acid, slightly soluble in pyridine. It dissolves in concentrated

sulphuric acid with a deep-violet colour (Found: $N=15.09$. $C_{24}H_{12}ON_4$ requires $N=15.05$ per cent.).

o-Diphenylene-2:3-phenazino-iminazole.

The greenish mass produced by heating a mixture of 2:3-diaminophenazine (1 gm.) and diphenic anhydride (1.5 gms.) for one hour at 220° - 240° , after having been boiled several times with alcohol and then thoroughly washed with hot pyridine, crystallised from nitrobenzene as greenish-yellow needles, not melting below 290° .

It is insoluble in ether, alcohol or pyridine but readily soluble in nitrobenzene. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives a blood-red colouration (Found: $N=13.94$. $C_{28}H_{14}ON_4$ requires $N=14.07$ per cent.).

4:5-Phenazino-2-phenyliminazole.

2:3-Diaminophenazine (0.5 gm.) and 30 c.c. of benzaldehyde were heated until the solid completely dissolved, when on cooling brown crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with ether and finally recrystallised from alcohol in beautiful, brown, shining needles, not melting below 290° .

It dissolves in alcohol with green fluorescence. It is insoluble in water and soluble in benzene. With strong sulphuric acid it gives a blood-red colouration (Found: $N=18.61$. $C_{19}H_{13}N_4$ requires $N=18.92$ per cent.).

4'-Methoxy-4:5-phenazino-2-phenyliminazole.

A mixture of 2:3-diaminophenazine (1 gm.) and anisaldehyde (5 c.c.) was gently heated until the solid

dissolved and then boiled for one minute. The brown precipitate, obtained by adding ether to the cooled solution, separated from nitrobenzene in orange-yellow rectangular plates, not melting below 270° .

It is insoluble in water or ether but soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, nitrobenzene or pyridine. It dissolves in warm dilute caustic soda solution with a red colour and in strong sulphuric acid with a deep-blue colour. (Found: $N=17.03$. $C_{20}H_{14}ON_4$ requires $N=17.17$ per cent.)

3'-Nitro-4 : 5-phenazino-2-phenyliminazole.

The black precipitate, produced by heating for four minutes a mixture of separate solutions of 0.5 gm. of 2 : 8-diaminophenazine in 40 c.c. of hot water containing 2 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 0.8 gm. of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in 30 c.c. of hot water containing 4 c.c. of alcohol, was first boiled with dilute ammonia for half an hour and finally crystallised from nitrobenzene in clusters of orange-yellow needles not melting below 300° .

It is insoluble in water or dilute hydrochloric acid, moderately soluble in alcohol and soluble in nitrobenzene or acetic acid. Warm caustic soda solution dissolves it with a red colour. (Found: $N=20.00$. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_5$ requires $N=20.52$ per cent.).

4'-Dimethylamino-4:5-phenazino-2-phenyliminazole.

The precipitate, produced by heating 0.5 gm. of the phenazine and 0.8 gm. of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in 64 c.c. of water containing 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 15 minutes, after having been freed from hydrochloric acid by boiling with ammonia, separated from nitrobenzene in chocolate-red shining needles, not melting below 290° .

It is insoluble in water, ether or dilute hydrochloric acid, difficultly soluble in alcohol, and readily soluble in

acetic acid, pyridine or nitrobenzene. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives a blood-red colouration. (Found : $N = 20.42$. $C_{21}H_{17}N_3$ requires $N = 20.64$ per cent.).

Dihydroxy-phenazino-quinoxoline.

The dark solution produced by heating 0.5 gm. of 2 : 3-diaminophenazine and 2 c.c. of oxalyl chloride in 80 c.c. of boiling nitrobenzene for 15 minutes was filtered hot and it deposited, on dilution with ether, a brown precipitate which could not be crystallised. It was purified by repeatedly dissolving in dilute ammonia and precipitating by dilute hydrochloric acid; m. p. above 280° . It is insoluble in the common organic solvents. It dissolves in dilute ammonia or caustic soda solution. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives a blood-red colouration. (Found : $N = 21.52$. $C_{14}H_8O_2N_4$ requires $N = 21.21$ per cent.).

2 : 3-Phenazino-azoimide.

2 : 3-Diaminophenazine (1 gm.) dissolved in 100 c.c. of water containing 5 c.c. of strong hydrochloric acid was diazotised in the usual way with 3 gms. of potassium nitrite. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature (33°) until the evolution of nitrogen oxide ceased. The precipitate obtained was washed first with water, then with a solution of sodium acetate and again with water, and finally crystallised from nitrobenzene in golden-yellow shining needles, melting at 280° .

It is practically insoluble in water, ether, alcohol, acetic acid or dilute hydrochloric acid but soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene. It dissolves in dilute caustic soda solution with a deep-red colour and in strong sulphuric acid with a blood-red colour. (Found : $N = 31.01$. $C_{12}H_7N_3$ requires $N = 31.67$ per cent.).

2-o-Tolylureide of 3-Aminophenazine.

The precipitate, which separated on adding water containing a little common salt to the solution obtained by boiling 1 gm. of 2:3-diaminophenazine and 1.5 gms. of *o*-tolyl mustard oil in 50 c.c. of glacial acetic acid for half an hour, crystallised from alcohol in violet needles, not melting below 300°.

It is soluble in alcohol, hot water or dilute hydrochloric acid. It gives a green colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found : N = 19.91. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N = 19.47 per cent.).

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Dithiocatechol.

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Although dithiocatechol has been described (Pollak, *Monatsh.*, 1918, 34, 1673), its activity towards ring-closing agents has not been recorded. The present work was undertaken with a view to synthesise various ring compounds of sulphur derived from dithiocatechol. Dithiocatechol was originally obtained by Pollak (*loc. cit.*) by the reduction of benzene *o*-disulphonic acid. We